

THE CONCEPTS OF “WISDOM” AND “FOOLISHNESS” IN THE LINGUISTIC VIEW OF THE WORLD

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Annotation: in this article, the concepts of wisdom and foolishness are analyzed linguistically, psychologically and philosophically, and the results of the analysis will help to understand these concepts more closely.

The concept of wisdom expresses certain skills, abilities and characteristics of an individual associated with mental activity, and thus is distinguished from other concepts about the inner world of a person by his cherished position (status). The mind that defines man is also a feature that distinguishes him from animals, while at the same time differentiating people from each other, serving as the main term in this research work. When conducting Cognitive Research, the concept of wisdom in Uzbek and English and its concept of antinomy were chosen by foolishness.

From the point of view of methodology, it is advisable to start the study of concepts from the areas of their existence, where these concepts demonstrate objectified types of consciousness. For the mind, these are the spheres of existence of ordinary/linguistic consciousness and special-scientific and religious consciousness. [1, 287] The last two areas of concept existence are reflected in certain types of discourse(discourse), which in turn are types of complex communicative phenomenon, which, in addition to the text necessary for understanding speech, include extralinguistic factors (knowledge of the universe, views, attitudes and goals of the applicant). The discourse obtained in the sum of pragmatic, socio-cultural and psychological factors is involved in the interaction of humans with each other and their mechanisms of consciousness as “buried in life” speech, and at the same time allows us to identify the most important aspects of the structural concepts that make it up.

Unlike linguistics, the philosophical and scientific imagination systematized within the framework of various concepts is universal, relatively clear and detailed,

and in order to reach its nature and essence, it assumes their explanation(exploration).

In particular, the concept of consciousness can be understood differently from different points of view. From the point of view of psychology, wisdom is a generalized characteristic of a person's cognitive capabilities (in contrast to emotion and will). In a narrow sense, it is an individual-psychological description of the mental abilities of an individual. In Applied Psychology, it is considered as a means of influencing the mind. [5, 165]

Wisdom (or intellect) in philosophy (Latin, intellectus-perception, perception, understanding, knowledge) - the brain with the ability to receive, store, modify and release information, develop new knowledge, make rational based decisions, control activities for the formation and achievement of goals, assess situations that occur in the outside world is a special function of the psychic activity of highly developed, complex differentiated (differentiated, differentiated) organisms. An important source of information that is processed and modified by wisdom and the knowledge developed for them, the object of the application of decisions and goals is the objective universe. In this sense, the mental or intellectual activity of a person is a perception of objective reality based on the transformation of the two.

In European philosophy, it is traditionally customary to distinguish intelligence and cognition as the main levels of intellectual activity. Wisdom is seen as an intellectual activity that does not go beyond the norms and standards developed in the socio-historical and cultural process and during individual activities, and consciousness is seen as the Supreme creative ability of the mind to create fundamentally new knowledge and realize the deep essence of reality. [3,341]

Metaphysical and Natural Scientific Materialism traces wisdom to the neurophysiological activity of the brain. Dialectical materialism recognizes intelligence and psychic activity as a function of the brain as a whole, but it cannot be fully integrated into neurophysiological processes, since in the process of social and cultural development of mankind it works with information-carrying symbols, is formed and developed on the basis of changing socio-historical practice.

Logical dictionaries interpret wisdom as rational thinking. Wisdom should not be compared, on the one hand, with intuition (intuition), and on the other, with consciousness and rational thinking at all. Intuition (intuition), the connection and

difference between mind and mind do not correspond to a clear logical definition due to the priority of the concepts of intuition and thinking. [4,579]

Foolishness is the complete or partial absence of reason, rational thinking. The simplest manifestation of stupidity, the complete lack of intelligence, is called madness. Another form of stupidity, the partial lack of intelligence, is called ignorance (actually stupidity). Such stupidity is a characteristic sign of many absolutely healthy people. [2, 402] Foolishness is evidenced by the limitations of intuition (intuition) and thinking, two main aspects of rational(rational) thinking. In cases where intuition is limited, they say that a person "does not feel subtle aspects", "does not understand the deep (original) meaning of the subject", is stupid in meanings such as "think foolishly".

In conclusion, our being is antinomic, so wisdom in the language is contrasted with foolishness, it is this fact that was the impetus for the choice of the concept of stupidity in the world of Uzbek and English for research.

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